

Some Thoughts on the New Origin Myth

Stories on Life -part II

“Every origin myth is a tale of creation: origin myths describe how some reality came into existence. In many cases, origin myths also justify the established order by explaining that it was established by sacred forces. A myth about the origin of some part of the world necessarily presupposes the existence of the world—which, for many cultures, presupposes a cosmogonic myth. Nearly every sacred story describes events that established a new paradigm for human behavior, and thus nearly every sacred story is a story about a creation.” (Wikipedia)

The New Origin Myth

Today we have no choice but to accept the fact that the world as we know it, especially in a social and cultural sense, has ended. In the last few years it simply collapsed and many of its institutions, formal and informal, began losing their meanings and purpose.*) In a way, we went through a kind of an apocalypse and a different world now starts to emerge revealing its initial features/ properties we cannot clearly recognize and understand yet. Thus, many institutions like schools, museums, or social life, will change, either transform or become marginalized, leading to the gradual decay of the entire existential infrastructure. Therefore, some kind of new common narrative/ myth has to be invented/ articulated. Perhaps, this time it could be a story that will begin with the birth of the observer and the observed, the emergence of life and its environment.

The two previous major and most important stories explaining the origin of the world in the West are the creation myth described in the Book of Genesis and in modern science the “Big Bang” Theory.

Since both these stories seem to become exhausted and obsolete in many ways, it might be necessary to establish/invent a new story, perhaps one in which the foundation is some kind of “Origin of Life Myth”, the emergence of life and its development, both biological and later technological/cultural. It will have elements of causality and connectivity but will not be exactly chronological, no dates, no years. Something that would resemble a story from the “high-tech Middle Ages”, which will also, at the same time, remembers Modernity.

One could notice that the present became overwhelming and exaggerated with too many details, while the past and the future are now much smaller, almost negligible and often without personal relevance like YouTube Shorts, an endless series of unrelated footage, or even more present-oriented TikTok. Like we are in permanent present as in fact we have always been.

The basic three-part structure of the new common story or tale could be: 1. Birth of Life; 2. Emergence of Consciousness; 3. Biosphere, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Alien Life. It is, of course, hard to predict how this story would look like when it is formed/articulated, but at least we could try to consider what might be the options.

This is just one possible version:

Part1. Once upon a time everywhere there was only water and land. Then, in some warm little pond a strange event happened. A few non-living particles connected forming a line in such a way that it starts separating itself from its surroundings. First thing it began noticing was that its surroundings could be “good” and “not-good”. Later “good” became “warm” while “not-good” could go in two different ways: “hot” and “cold”, both of these dangerous for its structural integrity. This was the “birth” of what will later become known as “life”. Later, hot and cold became “light” and “dark” while warm became “gray”. These were the first properties of the “world” identified by life essential

for maintaining its structural integrity (survival). Gradually, some parts of the string became “pictures of the world” remembering these properties and learning how to self-replicate and preserve the acquired knowledge. This is how memory was born. With time a bulb-like shape(membrane) was formed around the group of strings and the world became divided between the “inside” and the “outside”. Later, in the complex living forms, it became skin, cave, house, fence, fortress, border,..

Part2. When the inside became diverse and complex enough, at some point it started showing signs of consciousness of the world around it. Later became aware even about itself , as in the case of humans, and thus becoming self-conscious. Among numerous civilizations this led to the formation of culture, including origin myths such as the “Book of Genesis” or the “Big-Bang Theory”.Part3. Today we have to define a meaningful story that will take us into the “better future.” The foundation of this “new world” will be energy (electricity - from cell membrane to the entire planet), ecology and technology (primarily the internet as its “neural” network) including Artificial Intelligence. All these very much depend on human activities, except AI which at some point might even become an independent entity with certain self-conscious properties. It is in fact the real “black box” of humanity's future. If it develops as a “friendly relationship” it could lead to unimaginable progress. But if it becomes confrontational it might be the end of humanity. Thus, in the New Origin Myth this relationship with AI should be positive and good for humanity and all life on Earth. In that case the main negative character in the story will remain good old Death – end of Life.

Regarding the “observer” one of the key questions is: who and where is the observer? Since the "picture(s) of the world" depends on the properties of the observer and its position in relation to the observed, what is being observed doesn't look the same to different observers.

Observer can only be a living matter, while observed could be both, living and non-living matter. However, non-living matter including AI most likely cannot be an observer in a true sense, since observation is at the same time an interpretation/ understanding of the world.

It seems that the fundamental property of a living matter is metabolism, the relationship(s) between "inside" and "outside". These are various processes of exchange between life and its environment which also constitutes the distinction between these two("inside"-"outside"). Metabolism consists of three basic parts: input, processing and output; one of the most important metabolic processes is observation: perception, interpretation and memory. There is no observation possible without memory which includes self-replication as preservation and distribution of what is being remembered.

After dying, most living organisms cannot go back and become alive again. Interesting cases are viruses which are dead within a non-living environment and then become alive by entering a living organism and start reproducing. What makes the same structure become dead and alive in different environments? Also, when a virus is dead, what is the state of its DNA, is it also dead?

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 viruses have some characteristics of living organisms but lack others. However, regardless of whether a virus is considered alive or dead, its genetic material (usually DNA or RNA) remains intact and is not "dead" in the same way that a living organism can be considered dead.

When a virus particle is inactive or has been deactivated, its genetic material may still be present, but it is not capable of infecting cells or replicating itself. In some cases, the virus particle may be physically intact, but its genetic material may have been damaged or degraded to the point where it is no longer functional.

In summary, the state of a virus's genetic material when it is inactive or has been deactivated can vary, but it is still present and may still be analyzed for research purposes, such as to develop treatments or vaccines.

At what point a structure consisting of non-living molecules becomes alive? It must have happened with the emergence of the first living molecule (proto-RNA). Does an RNA sequence become alive when it has a certain number of bases, and what is this number (3 or 6 or perhaps 12) or, a presence or absence of certain atoms or molecules and/or their numbers? What are the conditions that initiate the transition from non-living toward living matter? Is there a minimal number of a certain atoms or molecules (carbon, water, etc.), or a certain basis or a minimal number of separate sequences with same or different properties that triggers the emergence of life ("Hydrogenising carbohydrate"-Nick Lane). Or perhaps life is one of fundamental properties of matter that is everywhere throughout the space, like gravity or magnetism, which appears only under certain conditions?

It seems that the main purpose of life is a sense of pleasure; the environment has to be “not too hot and not too cold” but “warm”. If at the moment of the emergence of a living molecule the temperature of its environment was T , then it must have been the ideal temperature for this life form. From its perspective this was “good”. When the temperature of the environment changes and becomes too cold or too hot, then this is “not good”. If both, inside living and outside nonliving environments are “warm”, then how can living distinguish itself from non-living? It would not be possible to distinguish between these two environments by measuring their temperatures. It shows that the key feature that separates inside from the outside world is the cell membrane which appeared at some point in early evolution.

Interesting question is how that happened, what was the process that led from the earliest living molecule to a proto-cell with the membrane? Inside the membrane is “good”- outside is “bad”, inside is “pleasure”- outside is “pain”. On the other hand, some “good” comes from the outside: energy, food... ”proton motive force”(Peter Mitchell). But they become “good” when they are brought inside through the membrane which is in fact a separation line (threshold) between these two "worlds". Life is movement/motion. It is a kind of change that enables forming the experience of time and space, entropy, aging...

It seems that similar questions could be asked regarding the emergence of consciousness as well. Perhaps it was the consciousness that, when appeared, enabled the recognition of life and its distinction from non-living matter. Then came understanding and interpretations of the broader world/universe and its origins(Genesis, Apple Tree, Evolution, Relativity, Big-Bang, etc.) that opens a possibility of the emergence of self-conscious Biosphere and perhaps even self-conscious AI.

Gregor Mobius, February 14, 2023

*) Quite a few thoughts and ideas presented here have been already discussed in some previous posts on this blog. This is just another try to approach these complicated themes from the perspective of the end of the existing paradigm. These incomplete thesis are just the best guessing based on some indicators visible in the world today.

Google
what are the top existential risks?

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Among them, at the top of the list, is **Superintelligence (Artificial General Intelligence)**. Somewhere in the middle of that list is Climate Change, which incidentally is not in any sense an immediate existential risk in comparison with bio pandemics or Superintelligence.

<https://sustensis.co.uk/top-existential-risks> :
Top 7 Existential Risks - Sustensis

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What are the top existential risks?

1. Artificial Intelligence (AI) Risk: The development of powerful artificial intelligence could lead to a scenario where the AI has control over humans and either intentionally or accidentally causes harm to humanity.
2. Nanotechnology Risk: Nanotechnology, the manipulation of matter on an atomic or molecular scale, could create powerful new weapons or tools with the potential to cause large-scale destruction.
3. Biological Risk: In the wrong hands, biological agents such as viruses and bacteria could be used to cause widespread harm or destruction.
4. Climate Change: Climate change could lead to

Appendix

Interesting example of media entropy is random selection of short videos presenting various unrelated footage in TikTok style one can also find as Shorts on YouTube. These are just shorter versions of thematic entropy which YouTube has established for some time now. One of the origins of this non-chronological structure, a collection of unrelated events, could be traced to old TV ads and, in some ways, earlier to the wunderkammer and library, going back even to the Bible. On the other hand, chronologically based History consists of mainly related chapters that meaningfully flow one after another. We should keep in mind that even each individual Short spot is, one way or another, itself chronologically based.

Perhaps this kind of structure could become a model for the New Origin Myth as well. As a series of short stories, often unrelated, it could help preserving the past. In fact, this is already the way how our personal memory is structured, as a number of important or unimportant events and experiences that can be recollected when needed. The only common property for these set of glimpses into the past is that they are specific for each individual. This is how a set of collective memories, presented as the New Origin Myth, could be structured as well.

YouTube Shorts

Worms in BANANAS...
8.6M views

White Blood Cells fighting under...
39M views

Hot dog under the microscope!
249K views

□ This Cant Be Anymore Clear 🤔
1.8M views

POWER OVER MIND - Strength...
170 views

Brilliant dance 💖
11M views

#shuffle
#shuffledance...
12M views

My Highland Cow
Babies
851K views

The dog is afraid of
cats in a stupor, they...
61M views

Snarky Thought of the
Day #225, Smoking
8K views

Boney M. "Rasputin"
shuffle dance, but it...
12M views

Hipity hop time for
breakfast!
6.8K views

Dancing is the best
cardio #keanu...
3M views

Raven Talking Back to
a Guy
2.1M views

The Cutest Blep in
History
1.2M views

Work it.
Shuffle/cuttingshapes
30M views

Can't Stop Watching
This Video! 🌟 (Kelvy...
13M views

Surprised cat
282M views

Shorts

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The best fun funny
videos pets 🐾 TRY...

I think I found a
METEORITE IMPACT...

Need Baby Moo Love
798K views

This Discovery Raises
Doubt About The...

Mysterious Artifacts
from Mexico

YouTube

All Music History Mixes Universe Sci-fi films AI Live Albums Scene Folk Rock Progressive Rock P >

The Disturbing Paintings of Hieronymus Bosch
hochelaga ✓
3.8M views · 1 year ago

What is Ultimate Reality?
Closer To Truth
32K views · 4 months ago

25 Countries With The Highest Rate of Atheism.
World According To Briggs ✓
2.8M views · 11 months ago

Palisades High School 1975
hi57
51K views · 11 years ago

What is the Point of Avant-Garde Art? (Death Grips, Th...
Bliss Foster ✓

THE SIGHTS OF SPACE: A Voyage to Spectacular Allie...
melodysheep ✓

The Animals - The Twain Shall... - Full Album 1968
MazNour II

La Petite Fille De La Mer (Vangelis)
Maria

All Music AI Humans Live Mixes History Sci-fi films Albums Quantum Mechanics Classic Rock Folk Ro >

'I Will Always Love You' Linda Ronstadt
catman916
9.7M views · 13 years ago

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RISE Conf
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